

ON THE FINITE-STRAIN-INVARIANT FAILURE CRITERION FOR COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The finite-strain-invariant failure criterion developed by Feng [1] is being evaluated with the experimental data for a boron/epoxy, symmetrically balanced, angle-ply laminate. The results indicate that the failure-criterion prediction agrees with the experimental data and that the failure criterion also predicts the matrix-dominated or fiber-dominated modes of failure. Two special isotropic cases in infinitesimal strain theory are obtained. The failure criteria for these special cases preserve the mathematical forms of both the generalized Von Mises yield criterion and the Von Mises yield criterion in plasticity.

KEYWORDS: Failure; Strain; Invariant; Composites.

1. INTRODUCTION

The maximum stress and Tsai-Hill failure criteria have been evaluated by Bert and Cho [2] for a boron/epoxy, symmetrically balanced, angle-ply laminate. In this paper, the same experimental data are used to evaluate the finite-strain-invariant failure criterion developed recently by Feng [1]. Since the strains to be evaluated are in the realm of infinitesimal strain theory, the finite-strain-invariant failure criterion has been reduced to the infinitesimal-strain-invariant failure criterion.

The failure criterion consists of two parts: the matrix-dominated failure mode and fiber-dominated failure mode. Five material properties are needed to determine the five constants in the failure criterion. These five material properties are, usually, longitudinal compressive and tensile strengths, transverse compressive and tensile strengths, and shear strength. In formulating the failure criterion, the strain criterion was developed. However, in most cases, experimental data are presented in stresses rather than in strains. For plane-stress

problems, four more elastic constants are needed to convert stresses into strains. These four elastic constants are longitudinal and transverse elastic moduli, shear modulus, and the major Poisson's ratio.

In this paper, the elastic and failure properties of a unidirectional boron/epoxy composite, obtained by Hahn [3], are used for determining the failure criterion. Besides these fundamental properties, Hahn also obtained the failure strengths of boron/epoxy, symmetrically balanced, angle-ply laminates with fiber angles ranging from 0 to 90 degrees. These experimental data for the off-angle, symmetrically balanced, angle-ply laminates are used to evaluate the validity of the strain-invariant failure criterion of composites.

2. FAILURE CRITERION

The failure criterion developed by Feng [1] is in the domain of finite elasticity and consists of two modes. The matrix- and fiber-dominated failure modes are, respectively, functions of the strain invariants I_1 , I_2 , I_4 , and I_5 ,

$$A_1 (I_1 - 3) + A_{11} (I_1 - 3)^2 + A_2 (I_2 - 3) - 1 = 0, \quad (1a)$$

$$A_5 (I_5 - 1) + A_{55} (I_5 - 1)^2 + A_4 (I_4 - 1) - 1 = 0, \quad (1b)$$

The failure material constants A_1 , A_{11} , A_2 (A_4), A_5 , and A_{55} are to be determined experimentally.

The strain invariants are functions of the Cauchy strains, $C_{\alpha\beta}$.

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= C_{\alpha\alpha}, \\ I_2 &= \frac{1}{2} \left[(C_{\alpha\alpha})^2 - C_{\alpha\beta} C_{\alpha\beta} \right], \\ I_3 &= \det(C_{\alpha\beta}), \\ I_4 &= V_\alpha C_{\alpha\gamma} C_{\gamma\beta} V_\beta, \\ I_5 &= I_\alpha C_{\alpha\beta} V_\beta, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where V_α are components of the unit vector along the fiber direction before deformation.

The failure of a composite will be initiated when one of Eqs. (1) is satisfied. The failure criterion can be reduced to the infinitesimal strain-invariant criterion.

The matrix- and fiber-dominated failure modes in terms of infinitesimal strain invariants are, respectively,

$$A_1 J_1 + A_{11} J_1^2 + A_2 J_2 - 1 = 0, \quad (3a)$$

$$A_5 J_5 + A_{55} J_5^2 + A_4 J_4 - 1 = 0, \quad (3b)$$

where J_1, J_2, J_4 , and J_5 , are related to the infinitesimal strain components by

$$\begin{aligned} J_1 &= \epsilon_{11} + \epsilon_{22} + \epsilon_{33}, \\ J_2 &= \frac{1}{6} [(\epsilon_{11} - \epsilon_{22})^2 + (\epsilon_{22} - \epsilon_{33})^2 + (\epsilon_{33} - \epsilon_{11})^2] + \epsilon_{12}^2 + \epsilon_{23}^2 + \epsilon_{13}^2, \\ J_4 &= \epsilon_{12}^2 + \epsilon_{13}^2, \\ J_5 &= \epsilon_{11}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Equations (1) in finite elasticity and Eqs. (3) in infinitesimal elasticity comprise the failure criterion for a composite structure.

In many practical situations, the experimental failure state is measured in terms of stresses rather than strains. Therefore, it is necessary to convert the stresses to strains. For plane-stress problems, the constitutive relationships that relate stresses and strains are

$$\left\{ \tilde{\epsilon} \right\} = [\tilde{S}] \left\{ \tilde{\sigma} \right\}, \quad (5)$$

where

$$\left\{ \tilde{\epsilon} \right\}^t = \left\{ \epsilon_{11} \ \epsilon_{22} \ \epsilon_{33} \ \epsilon_{12} \right\}, \quad (6)$$

$$\left\{ \tilde{\sigma} \right\}^t = \left\{ \sigma_{11} \ \sigma_{22} \ 0 \ \sigma_{12} \right\},$$

and the compliance matrix is

$$[\tilde{S}] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_{11}} & -\frac{\nu_{21}}{E_{22}} & -\frac{\nu_{21}}{E_{22}} & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_{11}} & \frac{1}{E_{22}} & -\frac{\nu_{32}}{E_{22}} & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_{11}} & -\frac{\nu_{23}}{E_{22}} & \frac{1}{E_{22}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{\mu_{12}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

In Eq. (7), E_{11} and E_{22} are longitudinal and transverse elastic moduli, μ_{12} is shear modulus, and ν_{12} is the major Poisson's ratio.

Another Poisson's ratio, ν_{23} , in a plane perpendicular to the axis of isotropy, can be obtained from the approximate formula derived by Christensen [6]:

$$\frac{1}{1 + \nu_{23}} = \frac{1 - \nu_{12}}{1 - \nu_{12}^2 E_{22}/E_{11}}. \quad (8)$$

3. SPECIAL CASES

The first few failure criteria, proposed in the past for a unidirectional fiber composite, have mathematical forms resembling the yield criteria in plasticity. In this section, two special cases are obtained from the strain-invariant failure criterion.

For isotropic materials, the failure criterion reduces to

$$A_1 J_1 + A_{11} J_1^2 + A_2 J_2 - 1 = 0, \quad (9)$$

where the effect of hydrostatic pressure is considered in the J_1^2 term, and the difference between failure strengths in compression and tension is considered in the J_1 term. The criterion has the same mathematical form as the generalized Von Mises yield criterion, developed by Yang [4], in plasticity.

Further reduction of the failure criterion can be obtained when one assumes that the effects of hydrostatic pressure and the difference between the failure strengths in compression and tension are neglected. With these conditions, the failure criterion is reduced to

$$A_2 J_2 - 1 = 0. \quad (10)$$

Equation (10) has the same mathematical form as the Von Mises yield criterion in plasticity.

4. UNIAXIAL STRESS STATE

Before comparing the failure criterion with the experimental data, the strain state in a loaded composite should be obtained. The coordinate system for a symmetrically balanced, angle-ply laminate is shown in Figure 1. The fiber axis and the direction transverse to the fiber axis are denoted by 1 and 2, respectively. A uniaxial load is applied along the x-axis. The lay-up of the composite is $[\pm \alpha]_{ns}$, where α is the angle between the loading axis and the fiber axis.

When the composite laminate is subjected to a uniaxial loading in the x-direction, the normal stress in the fiber direction (σ_{11}), the normal stress transverse to the fiber direction (σ_{22}), and the in-plane shear stress (σ_{12}) are given by Tsai [3]:

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{11} &= \frac{\sigma_x}{2} \left[1 + \frac{A \sin^2 2\alpha + B \cos 2\alpha}{\sin^2 2\alpha + B \cos^2 2\alpha} \right], \\ \sigma_{22} &= \frac{\sigma_x}{2} \left[1 - \frac{A \sin^2 2\alpha + B \cos 2\alpha}{\sin^2 2\alpha + B \cos^2 2\alpha} \right], \\ \sigma_{12} &= \frac{\sigma_x}{2} \left[\frac{1 - A \cos 2\alpha}{\sin^2 2\alpha + B \cos^2 2\alpha} \sin 2\alpha \right],\end{aligned}\quad (11)$$

where A and B are functions of the material constants

$$A = \frac{(E_{11}/E_{22}) - 1}{1 + 2\nu_{12} + (E_{11}/E_{22})}, \quad (12)$$

$$B = \frac{(E_{11}/\mu_{12})}{1 + 2\nu_{12} + (E_{11}/E_{22})}.$$

Hence, the stresses in each ply are determined for a given loading σ_x .

Figure 1. Coordinate system for a symmetrically balanced angle-ply laminate.

5. COMPARISON WITH THE EXPERIMENTAL DATA

The experimental data for the strengths and elastic properties of a unidirectional boron/epoxy composite were obtained by Hahn [4] and are shown in Table 1. With these properties, the material constants for the failure criterion (3) are

$$\begin{aligned}A_1 &= 481, \\ A_{11} &= 54,900, \\ A_2 = A_4 &= 10,000, \\ A_5 &= 76.5, \\ A_{55} &= 13,300.\end{aligned}\quad (13)$$

Table 1. Orthotropic mechanical properties of a unidirectional boron-epoxy composite for plane stress problems.

Property	Units	Boron-epoxy
E_{11}	GPa	206.7
E_{22}	GPa	20.7
μ_{12}	GPa	6.9
ν_{12}	none	0.3
X_{σ}	MPa	1300.0
X'_{α}	MPa	62.0
S_{σ}	MPa	68.9
Y_{σ}	MPa	2490.0
Y'_{α}	MPa	310.0

The maximum uniaxial stresses before failure for a boron/epoxy, symmetrically balanced, angle-ply laminate with various angles of orientation are shown in Figure 2. The basic strength data used in determining the failure criterion are shown as solid dots.

Figure 2. The strengths predicted by the finite-strain-invariant failure criterion and the experimental data (shown as dots) for a boron/epoxy, symmetrically balanced, angle-ply laminate.

As can be seen from the graph, the failure criterion is divided into two parts: the fiber-dominated failure mode and the matrix-dominated failure mode. It is worth noting that for a unidirectional composite ($\alpha = 0$), the criterion predicts that the matrix failure will precede the fiber failure. The data used assume total failure of the composite; therefore, the fiber-dominated failure mode is assumed for determining the failure criterion. However, the failure criterion indicates that the matrix-dominated failure occurs first for a unidirectional boron/epoxy composite subjected to uniaxial loading in the fiber direction.

The open dots shown in Figure 2 are the experimental data of the failure stresses of boron/epoxy, symmetrically balanced, angle-ply composite laminates. These values are not used in determining the failure material constants A_1 , A_{11} , A_2 (A_4), A_5 , and A_{55} . It can be seen that the failure predicted by the failure criterion agrees with the experimental data.

6. CONCLUSIONS

For special cases, the mathematical forms of the finite-strain-invariant failure criterion reduce to the well-known yield criteria in plasticity. Also, the predictions of the failure criterion agree with the experimental data for a boron/epoxy, symmetrically balanced, angle-ply composite laminate. The results also indicate that the failure criterion can be used to predict the initial failure mode of a composite, whether it be fiber failure mode or matrix failure mode.

7. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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8. REFERENCES

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